

Donor-Acceptor Complex of *p*-Benzoquinone and Hydroquinone with Amine and Polar Solvents

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The equilibrium constants of 1 : 1 donor-acceptor complexes of *p*-benzoquinone and hydroquinone with various aliphatic amines viz., methyl, dimethyl, trimethyl, ethyl, diethyl, triethyl amine and different polar solvents such as alcohol, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide have been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous medium. The results show that the donor strengths of the methyl and ethyl substituted amines studied are in the order dimethyl > methyl > trimethyl and diethyl > triethyl > ethyl amine. In the case of *p*-benzoquinone—solvent systems the observed order is dimethyl sulphoxide > dimethyl formamide > ethanol > methanol > acetonitrile.

Although large amount of work has been done on the electron donor property of amine^{1,2}, polar solvents³⁻⁵ and on the electron acceptor property of quinone⁶ and phenolic substances^{7,8}—but little work is done in aqueous medium. Recently, it has been shown from spectrophotometric studies that the donor-acceptor complexes can form between *p*-benzoquinone as electron acceptor and amino acids as electron donors in aqueous medium⁹. The solvents like dimethyl sulphoxide, dimethyl formamide, ethanol, methanol and acetonitrile are not inert towards some electron acceptors. The absorption spectra of *p*-benzoquinone in these solvents also indicate that the solvents act as electron donors during interaction with *p*-benzoquinone. To know the characteristic properties of these solvents as electron donors, it is interesting to study the equilibrium constants of these solvents with the acceptor *p*-benzoquinone and hydroquinone.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental details are the same as given in the previous communication⁹. Analytical grade amines are generally taken without further purification. Strengths of the amines have been determined by titration with acid of known strength. All the solvents which were used as electron donors were supplied by B.D.H. These were purified by recommended methods before use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The original light yellow colour of *p*-benzoquinone disappears when amine mixed with *p*-benzoquinone solution and reddish violet colour develops. After equilibrium spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Beckman model DU absorption spectrophotometer

at 35°. The equilibrium constant K_c and molar extinction coefficient ϵ_c of the benzoquinone-amine complexes were calculated with the Benesi-Hildebrand equation for 1 : 1 complexes as discussed in the earlier communication⁹. Similarly hydroquinone-amine complexes have also been studied. The spectra of *p*-benzoquinone and hydroquinone with methyl and ethyl amine shows charge-transfer band in the visible region which intensified with increase in the concentration of methyl and ethyl amine. Straight lines were obtained in all complexes by plotting $[b]/\log I_0/I$ against $1/[a]$ at 400 nm. Fig. 1 shows one such typical plot and the values of equilibrium constants calculated from the graph are given in Table 1.

TABLE I
Spectrophotometric results of p-benzoquinone and hydroquinone with amine and polar solvents

Acceptor	Donor	Equilibrium constant K_c (l/mole) 35°	$\epsilon_c \times 10^{-3}$
Benzoquinone	Methyl amine	1855	8.33
	Dimethyl amine	2563	8.62
	Trimethyl amine	1436	13.50
	Ethyl amine	2985	5.75
	Diethyl amine	3428	1.67
	Triethyl amine	3059	3.85
	Hydroquinone	Methyl amine	698
Dimethyl amine		815	2.27
Trimethyl amine		680	3.33
Ethyl amine		933	1.78
Diethyl amine		1187	1.12
Triethyl amine		1080	1.10
Benzoquinone	Acetonitrile	0.07	0.588
	Ethyl alcohol	0.10	0.833
	Methyl alcohol	0.08	0.833
	Dimethyl formamide	0.11	0.588
	Dimethyl sulphoxide	0.13	1.00

The equilibrium constants for the interactions of the amines with both acceptors show that the donor strength of the methyl and ethyl substituted amines studied is in the order dimethyl > methyl > trimethyl and diethyl > triethyl > ethyl amine. The electron donating capacity of the donors are related to their relative basicity and ionization potential. The relative basicity of the donor amine in aqueous medium is also in the same order¹⁰ *i.e.*, dimethyl > methyl > trimethyl and diethyl > triethyl > ethyl amine. So the results are consistent with the theoretical expectations.

The interaction of *p*-benzoquinone with polar solvents is very weak. The equilibrium constants and molar extinction coefficients of these complexes were determined as before. Since no absorption maximum was observed in the case of *p*-benzoquinone—alcohol complex, the equilibrium constant was calculated by measuring the absorbance at a particular wave length where *p*-benzoquinone showed more absorption in the presence of alcohol. The equilibrium constants calculated from the graph (Table 1) show that the donor strength of the solvents studied is in the order dimethyl sulphoxide > dimethyl formamide > ethanol > methanol > acetonitrile. The relative basicity of these donor solvents is also in the same order¹¹ *i.e.*, dimethyl sulphoxide > dimethyl formamide > ethanol > methanol > acetonitrile. The thermodynamic and spectrophotometric properties of the charge-transfer complexes of iodine, 2,4 dinitrophenol, *m*-chlorophenyl hydrazine etc., with these donor solvents also support the above order of basicity of these donor solvents^{3-5,12}.

Fig. 1. Spectral determination of equilibrium constant for *p*-benzoquinone-amine system at 35°C (1) triethyl, (2) diethyl, (3) trimethyl, (4) dimethyl, (5) methyl, (6) ethyl amine.

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REFERENCES

1. S. K. Chakrabarty and A. K. Chandra, *Naturwiss.*, 1962, 206.
2. J. B. Birks and M. A. Slifkin, *Nature*, 1963, **197**, 42.
3. P. Kalaboe, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1964, **13**, 27.
4. H. Tsubomura and R. P. Lang, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2085.
5. W. B. Person, W. C. Golton and A. I. Popov, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 891.
6. D. C. Mukherjee and A. K. Chandra, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1963, **19**, 731.
7. Richard L. Middaugh, Russell S. Drago and Robert J. Niedzielski, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 388.
8. Melvin D. Joesten and Russell S. Drago, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **81**, 3817; 1962, **84**, 2696; 1962, **84**, 2037.
9. S. Sur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (communicated).
10. Edward J. King; *Acid-Base Equilibria*, Pergamon Press, p. 302.
11. A. J. Parker, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 1.
12. Mukul K. Basu and Benoy B. Bhowmik, *Spectrochim. Acta.* (in press)

